

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

The effectiveness of Reprofitstacko as an educational game innovation related to sexuality education for urban adolescent females

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GSC Biological and Pharmaceutical Sciences, 2024, 29(01), 302–309

Publication history: Received on 30 August 2024; revised on 24 October 2024; accepted on 26 October 2024.

Article DOI: <https://doi.org/10.30574/gscbps.2024.29.1.0397>

Abstract

Sexuality education in Indonesian high schools is a complex issue influenced by cultural, religious, and educational frameworks. One of the primary issues affecting adolescents is the lack of access to comprehensive sexual health education. Education empowers individuals, particularly females, to make informed choices about their sexual and reproductive health, thereby improving health outcomes for future generations. In addition, school-based nutrition education programs have been shown to improve adolescents' nutrition-related knowledge, attitudes, and behaviours. Interactive and participatory learning methods, such as games, can enhance engagement and retention of information, this study aims to determine the effectiveness of the educational game “Reprofitstacko” related to sexual and nutritional education in adolescent females. A quasi-experimental study was conducted from July to August 2024 in 2 vocational high schools in Malang City. The sampling technique used was purposive sampling. The number of samples in this study amounted to 70 female students. The provision of sexual education to young female aged 15-19 is crucial for promoting their reproductive health and empowering them to make informed decisions regarding their sexual lives. Comprehensive health education programs should address not only physical health but also cognitive and emotional well-being. Incorporating topics such as nutrition, mental health, and healthy relationships into school curricula can empower adolescents with the knowledge they need to make informed decisions. In this study, the educational game “Reprofitstacko” in urban adolescent female has a significant relationship between age and Sexuality and sexual behaviours and Nutrition.

Keywords: Sexual and Reproductive Health; Nutrition; Young Female; Education Game; Secondary Education

1. Introduction

Sexuality education in Indonesian high schools is a complex issue influenced by cultural, religious, and educational frameworks. Many parents and educators perceive sex education as inappropriate or as merely teaching sexual intercourse, which contributes to a lack of formal instruction in schools [1,2]. This perception is particularly pronounced in a predominantly Muslim society where discussions about sexuality are often considered taboo [1,3]. Sexuality education is critical to achieving the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), particularly health, gender equality, and education. The SDGs emphasise the importance of inclusive and equitable quality education (SDG 4) and the promotion of lifelong learning opportunities for all, which includes comprehensive sexuality education (CSE) as a fundamental aspect of health education and empowerment [4,5]. CSE not only addresses issues of disease prevention and reproductive health but also encompasses broader themes of sexual rights, gender identity, and personal empowerment, aligning with the SDGs' commitment to leaving no one behind [6,7].

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One of the primary issues affecting adolescents is the lack of access to comprehensive sexual health education. Many adolescents receive insufficient information about sexual and reproductive health (SRH), which can lead to uninformed decision-making regarding sexual activities [8,9]. In many regions, sexual health education is either not included in school curricula or is delivered in a manner that fails to address the complexities of adolescent sexuality [9]. This lack of education can result in increased rates of unintended pregnancies and sexually transmitted infections (STIs), including HIV [10,11].

Education empowers individuals, particularly female, to make informed choices about their sexual and reproductive health, thereby improving health outcomes for future generations [12,13]. Evidence suggests that educating female leads to better health for their children and contributes to the overall well-being of communities [12]. The Indonesian national curriculum, particularly the 2013 Curriculum, has made attempts to incorporate elements of CSE, although its implementation has been inconsistent across different regions [2,14]. The curriculum aims to produce well-rounded individuals by integrating various subjects, including health education, which encompasses aspects of sexuality [14].

Sexuality education plays a crucial role in empowering adolescent females. Studies have shown that comprehensive sex education can lead to improved knowledge about sexual health, reduced rates of teenage pregnancy, and healthier sexual behaviours [15]. For instance, a systematic review indicated that CSE programs significantly reduced the likelihood of adolescents engaging in risky sexual behaviours [15]. Moreover, addition school-based nutrition education programs have been shown to improve adolescents' nutrition-related knowledge, attitudes, and behaviours. A study in rural China highlighted that interactive and participative components in nutrition education significantly enhanced students' understanding of healthy dietary habits [16].

Interactive and participatory learning methods, such as workshops, role-playing, and games, can enhance engagement and retention of information. For instance, a nutrition education program that utilized games to teach about balanced diets resulted in significant improvements in adolescents' knowledge and dietary practices [17]. Similarly, incorporating interactive elements into sex education can help demystify topics and encourage adolescents to ask questions and express concerns in a safe environment [18,19]. Games can create a non-threatening environment where adolescents feel comfortable discussing sensitive topics. Participatory design approaches that involve adolescents in the development of educational games can ensure that the content is relevant and relatable, thereby fostering open dialogue about sexual health [16,20]. This collaborative approach not only empowers adolescents but also encourages them to engage with their peers and parents in discussions about sexual health, thereby enhancing communication skills and reducing stigma [20]. Due to this situation, this study aims to determine the effectiveness of the educational game "REPROFITSTACKO" related to sexual and nutritional education in adolescent females.

2. Material and methods

The quasi-experimental study was conducted from July to August 2024 in 2 vocational high schools in Malang City. The sampling technique used was purposive sampling. The inclusion criteria in this study include students registered at the school concerned, willing to be a sample and present during 4 meetings. The exclusion criteria in the study were students who did not attend at least once during the study. The number of samples in this study amounted to 70 female students. The treatment was carried out with the REPROFITSTACKO educational game (Reproductive Health: Fit and Active with Uno Stacko), which is an educational game modified from the UNO Stacko game. This educational game displays case questions related to relationships, values, rights, culture, and sexuality; understanding gender; violence and staying safe; skills for health and well-being; human body and development; sexuality and sexual behaviour; sexual and reproductive health; nutrition; and physical activity that must be answered by students and discussed with the group regarding the best answer related to the case. Ethics approval was received from the State University of Malang Research Ethics Committee. Student consent was obtained from all participating students.

3. Results

Table 1 Distribution of Respondents by Age

Characteristics	Mean	Min – Max	Std.Deviation
Age	16.61	15.00 - 19.00	1.011

The results of the analysis showed that the average age of respondents was 16.61, with the youngest being 15.0 and the oldest being 19.0.

Table 2 Distribution of Respondents Based on Gender and Grade

Characteristics	n	%
Gender		
Male	0	0.0
Female	70	100.0
Class		
10	12	17.1
11	27	38.6
12	31	44.3

The analysis's results showed that the majority of respondents were female (100.0%) and most were in grade 12 (44.3%).

Table 3 Distribution of Respondents Based on Relationships, Values, Rights, Culture, and Sexuality, Understanding Gender, Violence and Staying Safe, Skills for Health and well-being, Human Body and Development, Sexuality and Sexual Behavior, Sexual and Reproductive Health, and Nutrition

Characteristics	n	%
Relationships		
Bad	0	0.0
Medium	39	55.7
Good	31	44.3
Value, rights, culture, and sexuality		
Bad	1	1.4
Medium	17	24.3
Good	52	74.3
Understanding gender		
Bad	3	4.3
Medium	49	70.0
Good	18	25.7
Violence and Staying Safe		
Bad	2	2.9
Medium	7	10.0
Good	61	87.1
Skills for health and well-being		
Bad	13	18.6
Medium	20	28.6
Good	37	52.9
Human body and development		

Bad	2	2.9
Medium	28	40.0
Good	40	57.1
Sexuality and sexual behaviour		
Bad	7	10.0
Medium	6	8.6
Good	57	81.4
Sexual and reproductive health		
Bad	0	0.0
Medium	32	45.7
Good	38	54.3
Nutrition		
Bad	1	1.4
Medium	27	38.6
Good	42	60.0

The results of the analysis showed that most respondents had moderate relationships (55.7%), had good values, rights, culture, and sexuality (87.1%), moderate gender understanding (70.0%), had good violence and staying safe (87.1%), had good skills for health and well-being (52.9%), had good human body and development (57.1%), had good sexuality and sexual behaviour (81.4%), had good sexual and reproductive health (54.3%), and had good nutrition (60.0%).

Table 4 Relationships between Age and Relationships, Values, Rights, Culture and Sexuality, Understanding Gender, Violence and Staying Safe, Skills for Health and well-being, Human Body and Development, Sexuality and Sexual Behavior, Sexual and Reproductive Health, and Nutrition.

Characteristics	P value
Relationships	0.358
Value, rights, culture, and sexuality	0.971
Understanding gender	0.438
Violence and Staying Safe	0.052
Skills for health and well-being	0.479
Human body and development	0.667
Sexuality and sexual behaviours	0.009*
Sexual and reproductive health	0.407
Nutrition	0.035*

*) p value < α ; $\alpha = 0.05$; Kruskal-Wallis Test

Statistical test results show that there is a significant relationship between age and sexuality and sexual behaviours and nutrition (p-value = 0.000; 0.013).

4. Discussion

The respondents in this study had an average age of 15-19 years. The provision of sexual education to young female aged 15-19 is crucial for promoting their reproductive health and empowering them to make informed decisions

regarding their sexual lives. This age group is particularly vulnerable to various sexual health issues, including unintended pregnancies, sexually transmitted infections (STIs), and sexual coercion. Comprehensive sexual education can significantly impact young female's knowledge and attitudes towards sexual health, thereby influencing their behaviours and choices [21,22]

In this study, significant results were obtained between the age of females and sexual behaviour. Young female who receives sexual education before their first sexual experience are more likely to engage in safer sexual practices, such as using condoms and other forms of contraception [22]. This is particularly important in regions where cultural norms may discourage open discussions about sexual health, leading to misinformation and risky behaviours [23]. For instance, Rahmani et al. highlight that despite criticisms of sexual education programs, they play a vital role in equipping young females with the knowledge necessary to navigate their sexual health responsibly [22].

In this study, it was found that nutrition was also significantly associated with female age. Adolescent females are at a higher risk of undernutrition and related health issues [24]. Furthermore, the dietary practices of adolescent female are often inadequate, with many lacking awareness of essential nutrients and their roles in health. School-based nutrition education could enhance dietary practices and nutritional awareness among adolescent female, emphasizing the need for comprehensive programs that address both knowledge and practical dietary habits [25].

Relationships, values, rights, culture, and sexuality, and reproductive health have no significant relationship with the age of females. Innovative approaches to sexual education, such as the use of digital platforms and peer-led initiatives, have shown promise in reaching young female effectively. These methods can provide a safe space for young female to learn about sexual health in a non-judgmental environment, facilitating open discussions and reducing feelings of shame associated with seeking information [26,27]. Additionally, integrating sexual education into school curricula can ensure that all adolescents receive consistent and accurate information, regardless of their home environment [28].

Moreover, the educational environment plays a pivotal role in shaping adolescents' knowledge and attitudes towards reproductive health. Research has shown that school-based health education significantly enhances adolescents' understanding of reproductive health topics, including the risks associated with early sexual activity and the importance of safe practices [29,30]. Health education can effectively increase adolescents' awareness of issues such as early marriage and sexually transmitted infections (STIs)[31]. Furthermore, innovative educational tools, such as digital applications and interactive media, have been found to improve access to reproductive health information, making it more engaging for adolescents [32].

This study also explains that gender understanding is not related to age in female. Research conducted at Diponegoro University shows that adolescent female has a good perception of gender roles and gender sexuality, with a percentage of 51.6% [33]. Empowerment programs aimed at young female, such as the "Girls' Voices" curriculum, have shown promise in enhancing self-efficacy and agency among participants. These programs focus on developing life skills and fostering a supportive environment where female can express their concerns and aspirations. By addressing the specific challenges faced by female, such programs can help mitigate the effects of gender inequity and promote positive health [11].

Violence and Staying Safe, Human Body and Development, and Skills for Health and Well-Being in this study gave insignificant results with the age of adolescent females. Interventions aimed at preventing violence against female have shown varying degrees of effectiveness. For example, school-based programs that focus on peace education and community social norms have been implemented in Afghanistan, demonstrating some success in reducing peer violence and corporal punishment in schools [34]. The recent introduction of the Merdeka Curriculum, which emphasizes flexibility and student-centred learning, provides an opportunity to improve the delivery of sex education in secondary schools in Indonesia. The curriculum encourages educators to adapt their teaching methods to better meet the needs of students, allowing for more open discussions on sexuality and health [35,36].

Urban adolescents generally have better access to health information and resources, which can enhance their understanding of physical development during adolescence. Studies have shown that urban adolescents are more likely to receive education about puberty and bodily changes through school programs and health services [37]. Urban adolescents may have more opportunities to engage in educational activities that promote cognitive skills, as indicated by research showing that urban environments often provide more diverse educational resources [38]. Social development during adolescence is heavily influenced by peer interactions and community engagement. Urban adolescents typically have access to a wider range of social activities and peer groups, which can enhance their social skills and understanding of interpersonal relationships [39]. Comprehensive health education programs are necessary to effectively support urban adolescents in their growth and development. These programs should address not only

physical health but also cognitive and emotional well-being. Incorporating topics such as nutrition, mental health, and healthy relationships into school curricula can empower adolescents with the knowledge they need to make informed decisions [40,41]

5. Conclusion

In this study, the educational game Reprofitstacko in urban adolescent female have different levels of knowledge about sexual education and nutrition, a significant relationship between age and Sexuality and sexual behaviours and Nutrition. However, the relationship between Relationships, Values, Rights, Culture and Sexuality, Understanding Gender, Violence and Staying Safe, Skills for Health and well-being, Human Body and Development, and Sexual and Reproductive Health to age did not show a significant relationship. This could be influenced by factors such as access to education, social dynamics, and community resources. By implementing comprehensive health education programs that address various aspects of adolescent development, stakeholders can empower urban adolescents to effectively navigate this critical period and improve their overall well-being.

Compliance with ethical standards

Acknowledgments

We thank all parties involved in this research for their support. This research uses internal funding from the State University of Malang Year 2024.

Disclosure of conflict of interest

The authors declare no financial or ideological conflicts of interest.

Statement of ethical approval

The State University of Malang approved ethical clearance (No.26.07.9/UN32.14.2.8/LT/2024).

Statement of informed consent

Informed consent was obtained from all participants involved in this study.

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